

B.ED. STUDENT-TEACHERS; AMBASSADORS OF CLIMATE PROTECTION

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Abstract

‘No Challenge poses a greater threat to future generations than climate change’

– B. Obama

With the escalation in the industry, economy, infrastructure and technology; the present era is also experiencing the negative and harmful effects of climate change. Since early 20th century, Earth’s average surface temperature has risen up to 0.9 degrees Celsius. This is mainly due to the increased carbon dioxide and other emissions into the atmosphere by humans. It is a time to take action to stop climate change. Therefore, the present education system should not only focus on educating the academic and co-curricular, but also on the climate change issues to the young generation. And for this, the teacher education institutions should prepare the future teachers to be completely aware about the changing environmental situations and its negative impact on the planet Earth. This paper discusses about the various activities that the teacher education institutions can plan for the student-teachers in their two-year B.Ed. program to disseminate the awareness about climate protection.

INTRODUCTION

Climate of Earth has changed throughout history. Most of the ancient climate changes were attributed to very minor variations. But with the beginning of the modern climate era and human civilization, Earth’s climate is now changing at a faster rate than at any point in the history. In the past 35 years the Earth is warming very recklessly. This global climate change is mainly because of emissions of greenhouse gases, deforestation,

industrialization and other unsustainable human activities. Impacts related to climate change are evident on the nation's human health, agriculture, water supply, transportation, ecosystems, and others. And if still measures to save climate are not taken, the climate change issues are expected to become increasingly disruptive in coming decades.

Therefore, it is a time to educate the learners about the sustainable practices to be followed to save the planet Earth from the adverse effects of climate change. This can only be achieved when the teacher education institutions shoulder the responsibility of imparting the environmental awareness to each of the student-teachers through their inclusive curriculum. The whole two-year B.Ed. program have to meticulously planned to organize various activities with respect to climate change. This will assist the prospective teachers to understand the seriousness of climate change issues and they will surely transmit their learning to the younger learners. Following content discusses about the few climate protection activities to be organized by the teacher education institutions;

CLIMATE PROTECTION ACTIVITIES TO BE ORGANIZED BY TEACHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

1. E-waste Bank; The present generation is inclined towards using technological devices in their daily life. The devices like laptops, mobile phones, i-pads have now become

necessities. And when they become non-functional or outdated, immediately the new device is purchased and the old one is directly dump in the dustbin or trash. The prospective teachers need to start an e-waste bank which will help to spread awareness about properly disposing these devices in their internship institutions. They should also gather all the unused technical devices. And, later provide the same to the E-waste management industries which will correctly dispose those technical devices, so that it does not harm the environment.

2. Lessons on Climate Theme; In the two-year B.Ed. program, the student-teachers spend almost six months in their respective internship institutions. This is the golden opportunity for them to utilize their proxy periods to share the details about climate change by planning their lessons. Also, the theme-based lessons can be given on global temperature rise, shrinking ice- sheets, rising sea level, kitchen gardening and other aspects of climate change and discuss the steps to be taken by the students for the sustainable development.

3. Activities; Awareness has to be created by the teacher education institutions about numerous aspects of climate change through various intellectual and creative activities like debates, essay-writing, slogan writing, poem recitation, poster-making and many more. Also, the similar activities can be organized by the student-teachers in their internship as well as community centers to spread the awareness of saving the climate. This will help them to lead and be accountable to tackle the issues of climate change.

4. Workshops by Experts; The teacher education institutions organizes various guest lectures on academic themes. Similarly, experts in the field of protection of environment have to be invited to conduct workshop on vermicompost farming, nutritious food-preparation, e-waste management, plumbing of leaking taps, usage of solar-power batteries and many more. They can also collaborate with the NGO's working for the protection of environment. This will result in getting the education and motivation to 'do for the mother Earth' from the experts who are practically working for the climate protection.

5. Visit to Farm; The student-teachers should be taken for visiting an agricultural land. This will make them realize the real picture of harmful effects of climate change on the yield. They will also understand the need and importance of organic and vermicompost farming. They will realize that, due to climate change the future is likely to see increase in salination of soil and water resources leading to the decline in yield. And will use all these understanding in acting as a climate change ambassador and also in their future teaching-learning process.

6. Wild vegetables exhibition; It is necessary for the future teachers to know, how climate change is affecting the health of humans. And to remain healthy the student-teachers should organize the wild vegetables and leafy vegetables exhibition during the monsoon season. They should spread awareness about the local vegetables grown like 'karkol', 'bharangi', 'math', 'bapta', 'alu che paan', etc. and also discuss the nutritional value it carries to fight the diseases caused due to the changing climatic conditions.

7. Street plays; Teacher education institutions should train their student-teachers to present street-plays on the themes like loss of bio-diversity, importance of organic farming, using renewable energies and many more. And these street-plays have to be executed by them on the road/railway stations/streets or any public places. This will help in making the common people understand the need of taking individual steps for discontinuing the climate change happening at the local to global level. Also, rallies and awareness campaigns related to protection of environment has to be organized by the student-teachers.

8. Millets festival; 'Healthy diet means healthy planet', therefore, the student-teachers should be made aware about the importance of different types of millets like sorghum, foxtail, finger, pearl millets since, these teachers will be educating the 'future of the nation' about the food items to be consumed in their diet. Therefore, teacher education institutions can arrange millet festival. Here, the student-teachers have to prepare dishes using various millets. Through this activity they will also come to know the benefits of consuming it and the manner in which millets are being produced i.e., without use of any chemical, thus it is good for health as well as environment.

9. Action research; In the fourth semester of B.Ed. program the student-teachers have to conduct action research. Here, they can spread the awareness about the climate change in their internship institutions by taking various environmental themes like carbon footprints, saving water, zero plastic usage, 5 R's (Refuse, Reuse, Repurpose, Recycle, Reduce) and many more. The action researches conducted on such type of themes will surely bring the required modification in the behavior of the young generations.

10. Climate Forum; According to a US-based group, New research from Climate Central, 'Mumbai could be affected by annual flooding from sea level rise by 2050'. This type of latest and current information should be shared in the climate forum. The student-teachers in the climate forum meetings should share their thoughts, ideas and decisions taken for the protection of the climate, they should also share their reflections of conducting sessions on climate change in the internship institutions. Also, yearly meeting has to be organized to know the work which the alumni are doing with respect to protection of climate in their respective institutions.

Thus, to conclude let us make our student-teachers ready to be climate ambassadors and to multiply the message of climate protection and inspire their young learners to be the young climate activists like Greta Thunberg and save the planet Earth.

References

<https://climate.nasa.gov/evidence/>

Understand Climate Change - GlobalChange.gov retrieved from

<https://www.globalchange.gov/climate-change/response-options>

<https://thefuturescentre.org/trend-card/environmental-impacts-climate->

[change?gclid=EAIaIQobChMIqOaQ673D5QIVAh4rCh3EUwRZEAMYASAAE](https://thefuturescentre.org/trend-card/environmental-impacts-climate-change?gclid=EAIaIQobChMIqOaQ673D5QIVAh4rCh3EUwRZEAMYASAAE)

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TNN (2019, October 31). 'Climate Study Sounds Red Alert for City'. The Times of India, Mumbai. p.1 & 2.